

Table 3. Grain yield and its contributing characters under waterlogged (0-50 cm depth) conditions.

Germplasm/ cultivar	Plant height (cm)	Days to 90% flowering	Single panicle weight (g)	PBT ^a (no. m ⁻²)	Harvest index (%)	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)
FR13A	158	145	3.63	135	23.1	386
Sabita	184	141	4.46	95	31.0	421
CR380-10	169	149	4.20	138	33.5	472
Matia	178	149	2.58	110	21.6	215
ARC18112	154	98	2.59	118	24.9	260
ARC18101	158	121	3.03	100	31.2	261
ARC18104	152	131	3.75	104	29.4	347
ARC18172	185	110	2.50	109	27.9	212
ARC18198	122	92	2.34	133	38.4	267
Tulasi	145	141	4.23	153	29.4	516
Mean	160	128	3.33	119	29.0	336
CV	11.4	15.8	23.2	15.2	16.3	30.8

^aPBT = panicle-bearing tillers.

(Table 3). For the rainfed lowlands of eastern India, plants with different maturity periods are desirable for different locations. Therefore, plant breeders could employ the genotypes mentioned here. ■

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Yield potential

Physiological basis of heterosis in rice

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New plant types and hybrids are physiologically more efficient. They have a higher biomass than inbred varieties and a comparable harvest index. Increasing biomass yield and maintaining a high harvest index are the main breeding strategies for achieving another breakthrough in rice yield. Biomass is a complex trait governed by a number of morphophysiological components. We attempted to analyze the physiological components of biomass and to study the character association and path relationship among its components. A strategy to select parents for developing hybrids and pedigree breeding based on physiological efficiency are outlined.

The material for this study consisted of 15 F₁s and 6 parents from a 6 × 6 half diallel involving diverse parents for physiological efficiency. The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications. Data were recorded on characters such as biological yield, grain yield, harvest index, days to 50% flowering, grain-filling duration, days to maturity, cumulative growth rate (CGR), relative growth rate (RGR), net assimilation

rate (NAR), leaf area ratio (LAR), leaf area index (LAI), leaf area duration (LAD), and leaf area plant⁻¹ at different growth stages. Correlation, path effects, and heterosis were estimated.

Grain yield, CGR, LAI, LAD, and leaf area at seedling, tillering, flowering, and maturity showed a highly significant positive association with biological yield. The cross, Jaya / Swarnaprabha, which exhibited a high heterobeltiosis for biological yield (54.9%), also showed a significant positive heterosis for grain yield, harvest index, CGR, LAI, and leaf area plant⁻¹. Characters that showed a negative association with biological yield did not exhibit any positive heterosis. It is therefore evident that, to develop heterotic hybrids, we should identify parents with high physiological efficiency in terms of CGR, LAI, LAD, and leaf area plant⁻¹. Because characters such as NAR, LAR, LAD, and leaf area showed a high positive direct path effect, direct selection for these traits should be effective.

With this understanding of the key physiological determinants of biological yield, the interrelationship among these components, and their direct and indirect effects on biological yield, we can make a better selection of parents. This approach should help develop superior hybrids and generate valuable breeding material for pedigree selection. ■

Physiological efficiency of rice hybrids

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Heterosis observed in hybrids is the result of various physiological processes that occur at different stages of plant growth. A precise knowledge of the factors that contribute to heterotic vigor would help to manipulate heterosis expression in hybrids. We made a study to assess the physiological efficiency of rice hybrids during the crop growth period and to analyze the factors that contribute to heterosis expression. Six promising experimental rice hybrids were evaluated along with the popular check varieties Samba Mahsuri and Chaitanya during the 1995 wet season. Crop growth rate (CGR), leaf area index (LAI), and biomass production (BMP) were estimated at 15-d intervals from 15 to 60 d after planting (DAP). Harvest index (HI) and grain yield were recorded at harvest.

CGR increased up to 45 DAP and decreased later in all hybrids and checks. LAI, however, consistently increased from 15 to 60 DAP and hybrids recorded a higher LAI from 30 DAP onward compared with the checks. The high initial CGR was not maintained to the later growth stages